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Possibilities and challenges for a phased array antenna system in ISAC: A hardware perspective

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ABSTRACT The upcoming generation of wireless systems is expected to integrate both communication and sensing capabilities by flexibly allocating resources, including hardware. Phased array antenna (PAA) systems are already vital in communication systems and radars and, therefore, have been intensively studied for several decades. Considering the availability of multiple review assessments for PAA implementation and signal processing, this article fills an existing gap by evaluating the hardware challenges and possibilities for sharing a PAA towards deployable integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) applications. Both types of applications impose tight and often divergent antenna-performance requirements, such as control over beam shape, scanning resolution, and side lobe tolerance. The inherent performance trade-offs, such as pencil beam for refined sensing versus broader beam for instantaneous coverage, highlight the complex design priorities that must be tailored to the application to achieve optimal joint system performance. This paper evaluates state-of-the-art antenna array structures and beamforming techniques in the context of ISAC systems. Although less popular due to their inherent limitations, passive beamforming networks are particularly highlighted for several proposed solutions, e.g., reciprocity and multibeam concept, and elaborated through a design and measurement by the authors. This article addresses the theoretical challenges that emerge while realizing a phased array out of a single element, their impact on sensing and communication performances, and finally, a summary of their mitigation techniques from the state-of-the-art. Selected simulation and measurement results from the authors support the discussions. The paper presents a set of PAA performance matrices for the ISAC system and their related joint benefits or trade-offs. The key enablers towards PAA sharing for ISAC systems, including quasi-circulator, gain-boosting lens, and electromagnetic bandgap structures, are presented, highlighting contemporary technological developments and related theoretical aspects. With the in-depth review, the authors also demonstrate proof of concept for the selected technologies through design steps, simulations, and measurements.

INDEX TERMS Beamforming, Beam Squint, Butler Matrix, Circulator, Duplexer, Electromagnetic Bandgap, Gain Deviation, Grating Lobes, Intelligent Reflective Surface, Metamaterial Lens, Millimeter Wave, Mutual coupling, Integrated Sensing and Communication, Joint Communication and Sensing, Phased Antenna Array, Polarimetric Radar, Polarization, Reciprocity Channel Beamforming, Terahertz, THz.

I. INTRODUCTION

The relentless advancement of wireless technologies puts wireless standards at the forefront of innovation. The future of telecommunica-

tion is evolving beyond the data links to understanding the surroundings and for radars engaging the target nodes in communication. This revolutionary approach, so-called Integrated Sensing and

Communication (ISAC) or Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS), is about sharing the wireless spectrum, waveform, or hardware for concurrent or scheduled data transmission as well as environment sensing. ISAC is showing immense potential in wireless standards, e.g., 6G (generation of mobile communication), WiFi (Wireless Fidelity), V2X (Vehicle-to-anything), millimeter-wave (mmWave), and Terahertz (THz) wireless systems [1]. Legacy communication systems are designed for spectral efficiency and have a limited allotted spectrum, mostly in sub-6 GHz frequencies. At the same time, radar sensing in consumer applications is limited to automotive radars utilizing millimeter Wave (mmWave) frequencies with multi-GHz bandwidth and more focus on energy efficiency. A joint system that can utilize the available resources flexibly depending on the communication and sensing needs can not only mitigate the spectrum constraints but also enable radar-as-a-service (RaaS), thus opening up new application possibilities.

We witness a recent trend to go to mmWave frequencies for communication systems with the advancement of integrated circuit and packaging technologies. Directive beams became a natural choice for communication systems with multi-GHz bandwidth to improve the link margin against the path loss at mmWave frequencies. This trend has reduced the differences between traditional radar systems and communication systems in two ways - (1) the availability of multi-GHz bandwidth in communication system bands that can support the range resolution requirements of automotive radars [2] and (2) the antenna systems are becoming more directive with the help of phased arrays antenna (PAA) compared to traditional non-directive sub-6 GHz communication systems. This makes an even stronger case for joint or integrated communication and radar sensing applications enabled by spectral and RF hardware, including antenna systems [3].

PAAs with broad and swift beam switching are becoming preferred in current and future wireless communication standards. With ever-increasing data-intensive wireless applications and rapidly up-counting device numbers, PAA facilitates the spatial reuse of valuable frequency bands. Furthermore, they fortify the sustainability of a network by eliminating unnecessary radiation directions, which positively impact the energy cost and human exposure. They, hence, are considered a critical contributor towards human-friendly radio systems. Similarly, PAAs act as eyes for a radar system by providing lateral coverage and range enhancement through

gain boosting. Phased-array-based radar systems have been very popular for automotive, airborne, and military applications, providing it the leverage to be an intensely researched topic. It has resulted in its continuous evolution and development over the last few decades, which rapid advancements in silicon and packaging technologies have supported. Recognizing the relevance of phase arrays in pure communication and radar systems, it becomes clear that the design of their joint hardware carries great significance.

Printed circuit technology (PCT) is swiftly replacing the waveguide for PAA designs because of its simplicity and cost. The state-of-the-art millimeter-wave (mmWave) planar designs are already reaching the technological limits, while sub-THz (>100 GHz) implementation remains constrained by the limited availability of suitable substrates. Due to minor fabrication deviations, short wavelengths make the systems susceptible to beamforming and matching degradation. As a result, alternative integration platforms such as ceramic, silicon, glass interposers, and polyimide substrates have gained research attention. These technologies approach the feature size down to $10\ \mu\text{m}$, in contrast to standard PCBs that typically approach $100\ \mu\text{m}$; on increased production-cost trade-off [4], [5]. Another notable approach is the on-chip antenna, which escapes from the lossy chip-to-antenna interconnects. Typically restricted to single-element or 2×2 arrays because of silicon-area cost, it becomes more viable for sub-THz and THz size apertures.

The published review articles indubitably cover state-of-the-art antenna arrays and beamforming networks (BFN) across various technologies, frequencies, and applications. Some notable works include [6]–[9], which comprehensively cover the implementation and the signal processing for the PAA system. Similarly, excellent reviews cover front-end hardware implementations for the ISAC system [3], [10]. However, the availability of literature reflecting the hardware implementation aspects of PAA in the ISAC context is scarce. This work addresses this gap on time, presenting a broad evaluation of the PAA implementation challenges, solutions, and key enablers for ISAC hardware. This work reviews the contemporary technology of antenna arrays, BFNs, and their design challenges for ISAC. It analyzes the potential solutions from recent research and develops the performance matrices for PAA in the ISAC context. It indicates the key enabling technologies for PAA sharing in an ISAC system with their joint advantages or trade-offs. Section II of this

paper reviews the state-of-the-art antenna arrays and beamforming/beam scanning networks. Section III presents technical challenges for PAAs in ISAC and their potential solutions. The discussion is endorsed with the help of selected simulation results and measurements. Section IV presents technologies that are potential key enablers for PAA sharing among sensing and communication on a use-case basis. The proof of concept for selected technologies is also given in Section IV, while Section V presents the future work for PAAs in ISAC.

II. STATE-OF-THE-ART PHASED ARRAY ANTENNA SYSTEMS

A PAA works on the principle of simultaneous excitation of mutually phase-shifted multiple antenna elements, generating constructive and destructive interference of electromagnetic (EM) waves in the far field. These interferences result in high gain lobes and nulls, respectively, so-called beamforming. The reciprocal process similarly impacts the receiving PAA, i.e., increasing the sensitivity in high gain lobe direction and vice versa. The antenna elements are arranged in an 'array,' keeping a fixed distance d (antenna spacing) from each other in a one or two-dimensional fashion. The elements are fed with the re-configurable time-variation or phase delay signals generated through a BFN. This paper reviews PAA systems as a combination of an antenna array and an associated BF network, as depicted in Figure 1.

A. ANTENNA ARRAYS

In recent years, Ka-band has gained relatively higher attention than conventional sub-6 GHz bands due to the developments for 5G. Beamforming at the base station has already been utilized in 5G, while the next generation may require beamforming at the mobile station level. Only limited recent research has addressed the practical integration of antenna arrays with size, cost, and power constraints in a mobile set. In this regard, a low-profile multilayer array has been introduced named "mesh grid" antenna [11]. This miniaturized array can exist with the PCB signal lines and exhibits a fan beam pattern. In contrast to the conventional assembly of arrays in the PCB lateral plane, this 1×16 array is introduced in the PCB multilayer stack, reducing the array footprint to just a single element. The beamwidth of the elevation angle (θ) is adjustable by changing the number of PCB layers used. Measurement results confirm a bandwidth of 1 GHz at 28 GHz center frequency where the impedance is

FIGURE 1. An N-element phased array antenna system. ' θ ' is the electrical phase shift and ' d ' is the interelement spacing

matched and a half-power beamwidth of 130° in the elevation plane. Scanning angles up to $\pm 70^\circ$ were possible, allowing for nearly a complete spherical coverage using two arrays. A compact quad-mode array is presented in another PCB-based multilayer stack [12]. Each antenna element is shaped like a rabbit-ear antenna set on both sides of the substrate. Using these elements, a 1×8 element array with a 5.5 mm distance between elements is designed and measured. A wider impedance-matched bandwidth of 25 – 33 GHz is achieved with a central beam scanning range of $\pm 90^\circ$.

The aforementioned designs achieve miniaturization and wide bandwidth, respectively, at the cost of a complex stack-up. Using Vivaldi antenna elements, [13] presents a straightforward single PCB-based design. An array of 1×8 elements is prepared with half-wavelength antenna spacing using both sides of a single substrate. An impedance-matched bandwidth of 1 GHz is achieved at 28 GHz center frequency, comparable with [11], with scanning angles restricted to $\pm 70^\circ$.

In addition to the fully planar designs, a mixed-approach structure with switched beams is introduced in [14]. The design consists of 3 planar sub-arrays, each having eight rectangular patch antennas. Each sub-array is assembled at 90° to each other and controlled by a switch. Hence, half of the hemisphere scanning was made possible. Elements are spaced at half-wavelength and exhibit a matched input impedance of 1 GHz at 21.5 GHz center frequency. Another switchable sub-array-based slot antenna array is reported in [15]. The widths of each slot are non-uniform to support a wide frequency range. A matched impedance bandwidth of 2 GHz at 28 GHz center frequency is achieved. Sub-arrays

are steerable to get beam tilts of 73° , 128° , and 20° .

The discussion above mainly focuses on planar-based antennas with single-dimensional sub-arrays. Hence, these designs are usable for mobile stations (MS) and base stations (BS). Since the power consumption of MS is limited, higher gain arrays are usually desired at BS to compensate for the path loss and improve the link margin. A beam steering mechanism is required due to user mobility. However, for BS, there is a relaxation of size, power, and cost, opening opportunities for non-planar antenna elements and multidimensional arrays. In [16] a modular approach is adopted to design a re-configurable antenna array. The array can be modified by adding antenna elements through coaxial connections. For example, a 16×16 array is reported as a dual-polarized planar modular antenna, functional from 7–21 GHz. The array achieved a scan range of $\pm 45^\circ$ over this bandwidth. This approach is a suitable option for base stations.

Recent developments in sub 6 GHz bands include a 1×8 tightly coupled dipole array designed with minimum element spacing of 0.17λ using double-sided PCB printing [17]. With a considerable gain of 7 dBi, the array covers $\pm 45^\circ$ scanning in broadside. The array assembly demonstrates an impedance-matched bandwidth of 2.2–6 GHz, covering 92.7% relative bandwidth. In [18], a 12×12 tightly coupled dipole array is presented with a built-in balun. A novel superstrate with a printed frequency selective surface (FSS) replaces the conventional dielectric superstrates. Covering 0.5–3.1 GHz bandwidth, the array demonstrates a $VSWR < 3.2$ for up to $\pm 75^\circ$ scanning. A comparison summary of discussed array structures is given in Table 1.

The reviewed literature represents the state-of-the-art in PAA advancements for wireless systems. Each work adapts its approach to the desired performance, making it suitable for specific ISAC applications. For instance, the large-scale 28 GHz prototype presented in [11] and the quad-mode wideband array in [12] demonstrate high gain and wide beam-scan characteristics, making them particularly suitable for communication-centric ISAC applications by enhancing link margin and supporting broad user coverage and spatial diversity. Studies such as [14], [15] propose switchable 3D coverage arrays, while [17], [18] introduce designs with wide fractional bandwidth, enabling frequency diversity. These features and the wide beam scanning capabilities are critical for tracking and situational awareness in radar-centric ISAC implementations. Furthermore, the Vivaldi end-fire array described in [13] and the

TABLE 1. State-of-the-art antenna arrays.

Ref	Array size	f_o (GHz)	BW (GHz)	Beam span (degree)	Max gain (dBi)
[11]	1x16	28	1	± 70	10.5
[12]	1x8	29	8	± 90	12
[13]	1x8	28	1	± 70	12
[14]	3x8	21.5	1	± 90	12.5
[15]	3x8	28	2	73, 128, 20	12.5
[16]	16x16	15	14	± 45	27
[17]	1x8	6	4	± 45	7
[18]	12x12	2	2.5	± 75	6.9

modular array architecture in [16] offer scalable and reconfigurable solutions for mobile and base station deployments. These designs provide enhanced flexibility, allowing for optimization based on the intended use case, whether for high-resolution sensing or reliable, instantaneous communication coverage.

B. BEAMFORMING NETWORKS

BFNs have been extensively used in radar and communication systems. Its application to both of these systems at the same time is not straightforward. The challenge is to satisfy the diverse requirements of both systems simultaneously. For example, a communication-centric ISAC system may prefer a stable beam to compensate for path loss but with a particular beam width for coverage, while radar-centric systems require a narrow beam varying or scanning over time for fine lateral resolution [19]. The challenge is elaborated in [20] for a V2X scenario, where tracking a vehicle with a pencil beam (as a point target) may not ensure communication coverage to the on-vehicle receiver due to vehicle size; hence, adaptive beamwidths have been proposed for sensing and communication. In literature, BFNs have also been used for self-interference cancellation in wireless systems [21].

The fundamental building blocks of a BFN are power splitters or combiners and phase-shifting mechanisms; implementable as active or passive blocks. BFNs have been classified in various ways in literature, depending on circuit implementation, feeding mechanisms, and geometrical configurations [22]. This paper categorizes the BFNs on the circuit-implementation basis as active and passive and then further classifies them into subcategories. Each subcategory is briefly discussed, focus-

ing more on passive BFNs due to their potential for ISAC.

1) Analog active

Active analog BFNs benefit from the most straightforward circuitry among all structures [23]. Each antenna element is connected to a dedicated variable phase shifter in the RF domain to form and steer the beam in the desired direction continuously. They are further classified as the RF path, the IF path, or the LO path BFNs depending on the placement of the phase shifter [24].

2) Digital active

An active digital beamformer is based on an advanced signal processing system that digitally controls the amplitude and phase of the feeding signal to each element in the antenna array. Each antenna element has its own RF chain, analog-to-digital (ADC) / digital-to-analog (DAC), and signal processing unit. In contrast to analog and hybrid BFNs, digital processing provides extended control and flexibility on the signal amplitude and phase, enabling accurate calibration and independent control over beam pattern, sweep, multiple beams, and adaptive interference mitigation. Digital beamforming is the most suitable type of BF for ISAC systems due to its rapid adaptability, hence supporting radar or communication operations, which is required. The trade-off is the high cost and power consumption of the increased number of ADCs and DACs on the hardware side and computation complexity and cost for the signal processor [24].

3) Hybrid active

Active hybrid BFN topology has been employed in reported research to achieve the benefits of a digital BFN, such as multi-beam, null steering, and digital processing while using a lower cost and power-consuming analog BFN hardware. Many antenna elements are connected to a limited number of RF chains. Hybrid BF is achieved by connecting each data stream to a subset of antennas through an analog BFN or connecting each ADC to each antenna element through multiple analog BFNs. These approaches are called partially- and fully-connected hybrid beamforming, respectively [23], [25]. Hybrid BF provides a compromise between power and device count against beam control with a fully connected topology that offers higher freedom at the cost of circuit complexity. Full-duplex ISAC has been demonstrated using partially connected hybrid beamforming in [26].

TABLE 2. Beamforming networks - performance vs. trade-offs.

BFN	Pros	Cons
Analog	Cost & complexity, Moderate power	Limited flexibility, poor isolation
Digital	Calibration, reconfiguration	Device count, high power
Hybrid	Optimize between analog and digital	Device count, Complexity
Lens	Low power, low cost	Large footprint, unused ports, fix beam angles
Circuit	Simple & scalable, low power & cost	Lossy, fix beam angles

4) Lens-based passive

They are inspired by optical lens technologies and are made up of homogeneous dielectric materials shaped as bifocal, grating, or spherical lenses [24]. One side of the lens is illuminated by radiating antenna elements, while the other side radiates the beam in a specific direction. A slightly variable concept is connecting the lens radiating surface to the antenna elements instead of radiating directly from the lens surface. The advantage is the possibility of integration of these lenses in planar technologies. This technique is used to develop Ruze [27] and Rotman lens [28].

5) Circuit-based passive

This type of BFN is most attractive for simple, scalable, and cost-effective implementation. This approach relates each array element to each input port through a passive microwave circuit. The circuit can be integrated into the same substrate carrying the antenna array. The number of beam ports (inputs) specifies spatial selectivity, while the number of antennas (antenna ports) determines angular resolution. The well-known circuits are the Blass matrix and Butler matrix [24]. Blass matrix is relatively flexible in performance, providing more control over the number of generated beams over arbitrary positions [29]. N input transmission lines are mapped to M lines via couplers, which control N uniform linear array. It is a lossy network with reduced efficiency. On the other hand, the Butler matrix is a popular choice for passive BFNs. It is an $N \times M$ beamformer where N is beam ports, and M is antenna ports, where N and M must be a power of 2. It consists of fixed phase shifters and quadrature hybrid couplers and hence

FIGURE 2. (a) The designed Butler matrix prototype on a RO4003 substrate and (b) its beam pattern.

provides application-specific design and scalability possibilities as both components are widely used in the RF industry.

Butler matrices with higher order of ports require several microstrip crossovers and an increased number of components. In literature, 180° couplers and reflective matrixes have been proposed to reduce the number of components and the planar Butler matrix has been reported in microstrip, coplanar waveguide, slot line, and CMOS technologies [30]. A typical realization of a 4×4 Butler matrix using microstrip techniques is shown in Figure 2, implemented in this work for a case study. Authors presents the design for operation at 10 GHz in the FR3 band, which is establishing itself as a strategic band for next-generation wireless systems due to favorable propagation and moderate bandwidth.

A typical Butler matrix shows a narrow band behavior that originates from the wavelength dependence of hybrid couplers and cross-overs used in the matrix. The limited bandwidth caps the range resolution for radars but may not be critical for several modern communication systems employing bandwidth-efficient modulations. Similarly, from a fixed beam pattern, we can deduce a limited radar lateral resolution; however, it may not be a point of contention for communication systems operating in a multipath-rich centimeter-wave band, e.g., the

FR3 band, due to its favorable propagation and bandwidth trade-offs. Butler matrices can enable limited beam steering in battery-powered mobile stations, offering a cost-effective alternative to multiple RF chains for active beamforming. This architecture also presents a promising avenue for augmenting communication systems with sensing capabilities, albeit with constrained lateral resolution. Additionally, both performance parameters, i.e., bandwidth and beam pattern, can be improvised through advanced RF and packaging technologies. Wideband couplers have been utilized in Butler matrices, enabling the fractional bandwidths $> 50\%$. As well as, a higher order matrix has been successfully demonstrated up to 16×16 , and two-dimensional BFNs have also been showcased, indicating the potential of this pure passive network [31] [32] [33].

Passive BFNs may not be a solution for on-chip implementation due to their large size and expensive silicon area. Nevertheless, advanced antenna-in-package technologies and RF interconnects provide an attractive opportunity for mmWave and sub-THz applications, where the device's physical size is inherently reduced. A great attraction of passive BFNs is their reciprocity due to being pure passive networks. A single BF and array combination can act as transmitter and receiver and hence possess the potential to simplify the transceivers' packaging task. It is particularly useful in cases where a single radiating array has to be used for transmit and receive, i.e., antenna duplexed system, where a conventional active beamformer would require a separate circulator for each antenna element in the array [21]. Such systems are required in several communication protocols exploiting channel reciprocity (further discussed in Section III-E).

In the context of ISAC, each BFN has unique trade-offs, summarized in Table 2. Analog active BFNs have a simple design and limited flexibility, making them more appropriate for economic systems. Digital active BFNs offer top resolution and beam agility, making them ideal for dynamic applications and precise control for both sensing and communication. However, their high power consumption is an issue for energy-constrained systems. Hybrid active BFNs harmonize between analog and digital domains, offering scalable solutions that are practical for the mobile environment and vehicular ISAC platforms. Passive BFNs offer energy- and cost-effective solutions. Despite fixed beam positions, their simplicity and low power consumption make them viable for communication-centric ISAC scenarios where high lateral resolution is not criti-

cal. Ultimately, the optimal BFN choice depends on the specific ISAC use case, system constraints, and performance requirements.

III. DESIGN CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS FOR PHASED ARRAY IN ISAC IMPLEMENTATION

ISAC applies exclusive and often conflicting requirements on PAAs. Contrasting the ordinary wireless (communication or radar) systems, ISAC demands simultaneous or coordinated operation for both sensing and communication. This article underlines key antenna performance metrics and associates them with tangible ISAC application design requirements. An antenna array design is complicated compared to a single element and requires more attention towards element interaction. According to pattern multiplication theory, a single element optimized for performance parameters needs re-optimization in an array environment. This is because the array pattern is the product of a single-element radiation pattern and the array factor. An N -element linear array arranged along the z -axis has its far-field pattern as

$$S_{AF}(\theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} V_n e^{jn(kd \cos \theta + \alpha)} \quad (2)$$

V_n is the n th element signal amplitude, d is the inter-element spacing, $\alpha = -kdc \cos \theta$ is the input signal phase difference between adjacent elements, θ is the scan angle. The frequent challenges are isolation, mutual coupling, grating lobes, gain deviation, cross-pol discrimination, upper side-lobe levels, and beam squint, each affecting the communication and sensing capabilities of the hardware individually. Application-specific challenges are also there, e.g., channel reciprocity. Furthermore, other implementation challenges also exist for ISAC implementation, e.g., Tx-spill over through antenna system. Additionally, an effective and practical PAA system design must ensure manufacturing and mechanical stability while minimizing the associated tolerances.

A. MUTUAL COUPLING

Radiation characteristics of a radiating element are affected by the conditions of the surrounding electromagnetic environment. In the case of a PAA, the elements are packed together with a typical mutual spacing of 0.5λ to avoid grating lobes. Hence, the radiation effects of the surrounding elements affect individual elements, causing a mutual coupling of the elements. When all elements of the array are excited simultaneously, mutual coupling affects the

impedance matching of the n^{th} element and the active return loss as

$$\Gamma_n = \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{b_m}{b_n} \tau_{nm} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of array elements, $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$, b_m and b_n are complex signals fed to m^{th} and n^{th} element, respectively and τ_{nm} is the transmission coefficient between them. The active return loss can also be further dependent on the beam scan angle, depending on the elements and array design.

Mutual coupling may introduce very high active return loss at specific angles, giving rise to scan blindness, causing loss of communication for specific users and missed targets in radar sensing. Mutual coupling depends upon inter-element spacing, element type, array gain, and beam width. Mutual coupling not only deteriorates the active element patterns and creates ripples impacting the integrity of the radiation pattern but impedes matching on specific beam angles, especially for wide scan angles. The communication-centric ISAC suffers from degraded beam positioning and channel estimation accuracy, leading to bit error rates and, finally, reduced spectral efficiency. MIMO communication links increase spatial correlation among the channels, which is unfavorable to multi-user and high throughput systems, and performance degradation occurs for MIMO radars. Mutual coupling distorts the radiation pattern, impacting the lateral resolution, angle-of-arrival, and Doppler resolution for radar-centric ISAC. The beam pattern distortion can lead to side-lobe level variation, causing a reduction in or false detection. Thus, mutual coupling is a joint performance parameter for communication- and radar-centric ISAC systems. An active reflection coefficient on a specific bandwidth, which arises during beam scan, can be regulated at the cost of operational bandwidth and beam width for communication services; however, it impacts the lateral scanning performance of radar by missing targets on specific angles. Ref. [34], [35], and [36] analyze the dependency of mutual coupling and active reflection coefficient on the beam scanning angles.

The inter-element coupling may also arise through existing metallic objects in the vicinity. Figure 4 presents the active reflection coefficient of a single element in 4×1 array in such a case. The authors used TMYTEK equipment for beamforming solutions for this experiment with 3 elements of its 4×1 array excited through an active beamformer BBox-Lite, while one element is under test and connected to the Keysight VNA. The red curve plots the

FIGURE 3. A photograph of the TMYTEK BBox setup for active reflection coefficient measurement.

impedance matching of the element under test when a metallic target is far away, showing an impedance matching 10 dB from 24–31 GHz. However, as the target approaches as near as 3λ to the antenna (which is still far-field), the active reflection coefficient of the element deteriorates, and an impedance mismatch arises on partial bandwidth. This phenomenon can reduce the throughput of certain users who are served in those bands for communication services.

A simple approach to mitigating the mutual coupling is increasing inter-element spacing on the cost of grating lobes (discussed in the following subsection). Grating lobes can introduce ghost targets for the radar. Therefore, this approach is suitable for communication-centric ISAC systems if they do not use any spatial multiplexing. A more relevant technique to counter the mutual coupling in planar antenna configuration is to consider the mutual coupling phenomenon during the element design process, hence producing an array naturally avoiding this phenomenon. Ref. [37] shows that the main contributor to active return loss deviation for wider beam angles is a high susceptibility change rate. [37] and [38] presents the solution to this challenge by sheltering the radiator with a wide-angle impedance matching layer. It can be a perforated dielectric layer that compensates for susceptibility through its capacitive nature. By changing the size of the perforation, the effective dielectric constant is tuned for optimal active return loss. Otherwise, it can be a metamaterial layer tunable for its effective dielectric constant. In addition to this approach, tightly coupled antenna arrays have also been used to exploit the coupling capacitance between elements [39] [40]. The downside of these approaches is that they enlarge the antenna size by changing the printed circuit board's 2D design to 3D.

The alternate way to deal with mutual coupling is to mitigate it at the array level. Defected ground structures (DGS) and electromagnetic bandgap (EBG) techniques have been helpful. DGS technique is a well-known solution to decouple the

FIGURE 4. Input reflection coefficient of a single element of the array.

patch radiators existing on the same substrate by etching out electromagnetic (EM) decoupling structures from the ground plane of the PCB, e.g., Ref [41] and [42]. DGS solutions add manufacturing complexities, especially for antenna packaging in multilayer boards. The dielectric layers underneath DGS must be removed, or the DGS needs to be re-tuned considering the core and prepreg of the stack-up. EBG structures, on the other hand, are periodic metallic structures that hinder the propagation of EM energy in a particular frequency band. When introduced in between the array elements, they decouple the array elements by increasing the surface impedance of the substrate and hence attenuate the surface wave flow [43]. Putting EBG can enlarge inter-element spacing, giving rise to the strong side lobes, which deteriorates radar-centric ISAC systems. DGS and EBG techniques can also be combined as reported by [41].

B. GRATING LOBES

Grating lobes are strong side lobes comparable to the main lobe, causing a reduction in the gain of the array. Radar-centric systems are more prone to failure in the presence of grating lobes than communication systems. They introduce false targets in the lateral scan and steal the energy from the main lobe, reducing the radar range. However, other than signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) reduction, the grating lobe does not hurt communication systems directly unless spatial multiplexing is employed. To avoid the grating lobes, the inter-element centre-to-centre spacing d must be [44]:

$$d < \frac{\lambda_{high}}{1 + |\sin(\theta_{0max})|} \quad (2)$$

where λ_{high} is the non-guided wavelength at the maximum frequency. θ_{0max} is the maximum beam

tilt. In planar circuit implementation, this spacing criteria is generally not problematic with moderate beam tilts obtained by PAAs on organic substrates. For example, for a conventional Butler matrix with ordinary radiating patches with inset feed, as given in Section II-B5, the theoretical element spacing is $\lambda/2$ producing a maximum tilt of 45 deg (inter-beam tilt of 30 deg). It requires $d \leq 1.7$ cm while $\lambda/2$ at 10 GHz is 1.5 cm. Hence $d \approx \lambda/2$. $d = 1.7$ cm is used in the PAA, and side lobes are 10 dB weaker than the main lobe, as noticeable in Figure 2. However, in specific applications, grating lobes may become prominent where a higher beam tilt is required, which decreases the recommended inter-element spacing, and in case a low dielectric substrate is used, e.g., polyimide, the required patch width increases, resulting in patch ends coming very close to each other to fulfill this criterion. Depending on the element design, this criterion can cause an intersection of the structures. In this scenario, a bargain must be made between grating lobes and mutual coupling. Inter-element spacing higher than $\lambda/2$ shows additional lobes beside the main lobe, equivalent to undersampling the single in space, creating aliasing in the frequency.

State-of-the-art solutions for mitigating grating lobes are either adapting the individual element design for minimum energy projection in the anticipated grating lobe direction or array engineering to reduce the unwanted lobes. An example of the first approach is [45], where the authors achieve grating lobe suppression of 11 dB with up to 60 deg degree of beam scan by introducing a dual-mode excitation element from two ports. Unequal phase signals are fed to the ports, achieving the elements' main lobe in the desired direction and nulling the power in the direction of the grating lobe. In this way, element spacing of one wavelength was made possible. In the context of ISAC, this approach can be an interesting solution by modifying the beam shape through the mutual phase of the input port signals. e.g., using switching beams for sensing and data links on a time division basis for optimum angular target resolution and communication coverage. Another way is presented in [46] by null steering using varactor-loaded square patch elements. Each element is connected to four impedance tuning circuits connected to each patch size. Using optimal tuning, 9 dB reduction in the grating lobe is achieved for up to 75 deg of the scan angle. The alternate way is an array design for minimum undesired lobes. Contemporary research achieves this by replacing traditional rectangular lattice arrays with triangular latticed arrays, as they

FIGURE 5. Visual description of array-gain dependency on element pattern.

have a naturally enhanced spacing range for grating lobe-free operation [47], [48]. However, this approach is only applicable to two-dimensional planar arrays. Another reported technique uses nonlinear or sparse inter-element spacing, which interrupts the periodicity, contributing to the undesired lobes and redistributing the energy [49]. This technique is also applicable to linear arrays. A combination of element adaptation and array engineering has also been applied for the best suppression of the grating lobe [50].

C. GAIN DEVIATION

The gain of a PAA is the product of element factor G_E with the array factor G_A . Typically, the planar patch radiator elements have their main beam in a broadside direction. It is an intrinsic property of the element that can not be changed during phased array operation; therefore, an ordinary linear array, with element spacing of half-wavelength and 0° progressive phase difference, has its peak array gain in the boresight direction, and the array gain drops for wide beam scan angles (beam scanning loss), as visualized in Figure 5. Hence, it is an irreversible factor in an array design. To reduce the beam scanning loss across the desired angular range, it is desirable to have the individual elements with wide beam widths [51].

Additionally, individual element beamwidth varies with frequency for a wideband antenna [52]. This results in the dependency of the array gain not only on beam tilt but also on the operational frequency. Gain fluctuations over the beam scan impact radar-centric systems by range ambiguity in the targets and target blindness on the angles with significantly low gain. Similarly, it lowers the spectral efficiency of the communication links for users in low-gain areas. The elements' beam widths across the operational frequency band must be consistent to avoid received signal strength fluctuations across the users. Lower inter-element spacing can also be helpful in gain-variation suppression at the

cost of increased mutual coupling and worsening active return loss. A simple and effective remedy is digital pre-distortion to compensate for the gain fluctuations; however, here, we discuss only the hardware solutions, as the scope of this article.

The state-of-the-art solutions to array gain fluctuation are designing the elements with ultrabroad beamwidths by sacrificing directivity and hence radar angular resolution or switchable beams on the cost of complexity and beam switch delays. Both solutions present a trade-off, i.e., stable beams with wide beamwidth are suitable for communication, while switchable sharp beams are for radar. The antenna of the first category has been realized using image theory where an electric or magnetic source is placed against an electric or magnetic perfect conductor, respectively [53] and [54]. Due to the wide beamwidth of the actual source supported by the tuned imaging effect, the achieved half-power beam widths (HPBW) were greater than 120° and 160°, respectively, in both articles. Moreover, multimode excitation techniques are also reported to provide very wide beamwidths, e.g., HPBW of 120° reported in [55] using simultaneous TM_{10} and TM_{20} mode excitation. The second category of wide band elements is switchable beams or pattern reconfiguration; examples are [56] 123° and [57] 140° uninterrupted HPBW by switching the beams.

Ultra-wide beamwidth elements exhibit low gain, making them less suitable for mmWave applications where the gain of individual elements significantly influences array gain. High-gain arrays are preferred in mmWave systems to compensate for increased path loss. Conversely, ultra-wide beam techniques are more appropriate for sub-6 GHz bands, where radar resolution is inherently limited by bandwidth, aligning better with conventional communication needs. On the other hand, Beam switching, while offering directional flexibility, introduces added complexity, additional circuitry, and switching latency. Although current silicon technologies can achieve switching times below 10 ns, such delays may still pose a bottleneck for high-throughput multi-user communication systems. Nevertheless, for indoor environments with relatively slow target movements, these switching times are negligible, rendering beam switching a viable and practical approach for radar-centric ISAC applications.

D. BEAM SQUINT

A PAA's purpose is to generate coherent beams with a similar front phase. Beam squint is the deviation of the beam angle from the intended value as a function

of operating frequency. The root cause of the problem does not arise in the array but in the BFN due to the deviation in the required phase shift of each element vs. frequency. Typical time-delay circuits or phase shifters in active BFNs do not exhibit a linear phase-frequency behavior, which appears as the frequency dependence of the beam tilt in arrays [58]. The beam-peak angle deviation at a frequency f is given by [59]

$$\Delta\theta = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{f_o}{f} \sin \theta_o\right) - \theta_o \quad (3)$$

where θ_o is the desired beam tilt angle relative to the axis of array symmetry at center frequency f_o . The beam squint problem is resolved by replacing phase shifters with true time-delay (TTD) using very long transmission lines at a cost in the design area. Moreover, phase compensation may be estimated when designing the power combiner/ splitter and phase shifter to achieve better beam-squint and upper side-lobe levels, especially for the wideband operation. Passive BFNs naturally avoid this problem due to TTD based approach. Digital BF can provide TTD in the digital domain; however, they have associated power and cost issues. Therefore, this problem is mostly associated with active analog BFNs using active phase shifters. Hybrid BFNs offer mitigation by exploiting TTD on the digital level and active phase shifters on the hardware of the analog BFNs network of sub-arrays. Since the sub-array has a relatively wide beam width, hybrid BFNs can mitigate the problem to a tolerable level.

Beam squint is generally not a limiting factor in narrowband applications; however, in wideband radar systems, it can lead to reduced signal returns due to the beam steering away from the target at specific frequencies—particularly when using narrow beamwidths. Interestingly, communication systems have explored beam squint as a valuable feature for resource allocation, particularly in frequency-scanning arrays and multi-carrier environments [60]. In such contexts, squint enables frequency-dependent beam directionality, facilitating efficient multi-user scheduling. More recently, ISAC systems have begun to leverage beam squint innovatively, transforming it from a limitation into a functional advantage for joint sensing and communication. Reference [61] and [62] use the TTD lines to steer the beam-squint trajectory, which in return makes possible the user localization using a multi-carrier waveform. Each sub-carrier has its peak power at a specific location depending on its frequency due to the beam squint effect. The users'

feedback about their maximum power sub-carrier makes it possible for the BS to assess the location of the desired users. This technique reduces beam sweep overhead compared to the time-domain search approach.

E. CHANNEL RECIPROcity

The wireless channel is inherently reciprocal, i.e., the wave traveling forward undergoes the same path loss and multipath reflections as the wave traveling backward in a steady environment. This channel property has been exploited in communication systems, reducing the training overhead in MIMO and channel reciprocity key generation (CRKG) in physical layer security applications [63]–[65]. However, to maintain the channel reciprocity for two-way communication in a multipath environment, the Tx and Rx antenna on a transceiver node must be less than half a wavelength apart to route the forward and reverse channel transmission through the same path [66]. This condition imposes challenges on hardware packaging for mmWaves where a few millimeters of Tx to Rx antenna spacing becomes comparable to a half wavelength, e.g., 2.5 mm at 60 GHz, resulting in different forward and reverse channel responses [67]. Due to the physical size of antennas, Tx-to-Rx antenna center-to-center distance $< \lambda/2$ is often not possible, and in some cases, it is possible to give rise to Tx-spillover issues saturating the receiver low-noise-amplifier (LNA). This phenomenon is elaborated in this work by frequency domain channel sounding of mmWave channels up to 95 GHz. A Keysight PNA with VDI extenders has been used with one horn antenna element on each extender. The setup configuration is shown in Figure 6. Extender-1 transmits a frequency sweep in the forward channel, and Extender-2 transmits it in receiver mode. The channel response is plotted in the figure with the blue curve. The reverse channel is also swept in the same way, providing the matched reverse channel response, which is noticeable by the overlapping green curve. To mimic the separate antennas for the reverse channel, the extenders are moved 5 mm laterally, and reverse transmission is recorded, and plotted with the red curve. We notice that even by 5 mm displacement of the antenna, the reverse channel shows a relatively different response, jeopardizing the true reciprocity of the channel. Therefore, the electrical distance between the transmit and receive antennas of a transceiver can be crucial for certain communication systems, e.g., those relying on reciprocity-channel-estimation or CRKG; however, it does not have a direct impact on the sensing performance of

FIGURE 6. (a) Setup for round trip channel measurement. (b) Measured channel response in mmWave range.

radar. However, for a mono-static radar, the reduced Tx-to-Rx PAA distance can lead to Tx-spillover saturating receiver LNA, strictly restricting the range. Therefore, we can classify the channel reciprocity as a pure communication-centric ISAC requirement.

The arrays' center-to-center distance becomes even greater for an antenna array, which is comparatively much larger than a single element. It is almost impossible to be less than half a wavelength. The solution to this challenge is utilizing a single transmit-receive array with an antenna duplexing structure, e.g., RF switches or circulators, with each element. For active BFNs, this increases the circuit complexity. On the other hand, passive BFNs are naturally reciprocal; hence, applying a single duplexer at the input multiplexer provides an antenna-duplexed PAA, which can ensure channel reciprocity even at miniaturized wavelengths. Commonly used duplexing mechanisms are RF switches, which are a showstopper for continuous wave (CW) radars, or ferrite-based circulators, which are not functional at millimeter wave frequencies. Other potential solutions are electrically balanced circulators in integrated circuits or quasi-circulators at printed circuit technology (as follows in Section IV-C), both offer continuous time (full duplex) operation on the cost of limited isolation.

F. ADDITIONAL ISAC RELEVANT PERFORMANCE METRICS

In addition to the challenges and solutions discussed above, several other antenna features and performance matrices are critical in defining the ISAC system's performance. This subsection summarizes a few of them, and although they do not hinder PAA performance altogether, they need attention to co-optimize communication and sensing.

- **Array Gain** is one of the primary advantages of the PAA, which is directly connected to the beam directivity or width. Radar-centric ISAC extends the range due to the boosted gain and refines the narrow beamwidth, which refines the lateral resolution in return. For communication-centric scenarios, improve the link budget. However, a narrow beam restricts the instantaneous coverage and demands increased precision to target the user with frequent beam switching or scanning. The higher array gain is achieved at the cost of hardware complexity and cost.
- **Beam steering range** is the lateral spatial coverage between the two extreme beam angles. A wide coverage, e.g., $\pm 60^\circ$ azimuth, is vital for mobile ISAC platforms, e.g., V2X systems. However, the wider steering angles worsen the gain deviation and are vulnerable to grating lobes, damaging the sensing performance.
- **Element count and aperture size** are directly proportional to beamforming gain and spatial resolution for radars. High element count enables fine beam control and the possibility to synthesize multiple beams through signal processing for multiuser communication and multiple target tracking. It also extends MIMO performance by providing an extra number of uncorrelated channels. However, it is directly in trade-off with cost, power consumption, and calibration complexity.
- **Beam switching/scanning speed** is critical in a real-time scenario. Fast updates are vital for seamless moving-user coverage and handoff in communication and real-time tracking for sensing applications. Scanning speed is usually dependent on semiconductor PAA circuitry. Predictive switching using signal processing algorithms is a practical and cost-effective solution for rapid switching.

Together, the discussed parameters form the most important features and performance metrics of a PAA in the ISAC application summarized in Table 3. Their careful adoption and opti-

mization with the challenges vs. mitigation solutions discussed earlier define antenna performance in a high-performance ISAC system. The optimization choice within the existing trade-offs is strongly dependent on the focus of the system, i.e., radar-centric (communication-assisted radar), communication-centric (radar-assisted communication), or radar as a service (a byproduct of a communication system).

IV. KEY-ENABLERS FOR ANTENNA SHARING IN ISAC HARDWARE

Communication systems usually utilize limited bandwidth with higher-order modulation to meet user needs. Conventional communication systems typically apply wide-angle beam widths to increase the coverage. Nevertheless, user-directed pencil beams are being applied in mmWave communication systems to counter the higher path loss. In contrast, radar systems typically prefer higher bandwidth for better range resolution, using narrow beams and sweeping the coverage area to provide better lateral resolution. There are still specific application areas where various technologies and RF blocks can potentially use a shared PAA for communication and radar systems.

A. MILLIMETER WAVE AND sub-THz ANTENNA FRONT-ENDS

Advances in semiconductor and packaging technology have enabled the commercial deployment of mmWave (>30 GHz) and sub-THz (>100 GHz) front-ends. They offer significant advantages for ISAC compared to conventional low-frequency bands, particularly in terms of data throughput and sensing resolution. Fine range resolution demands wideband waveforms, which are now possible by exploiting the sub-THz bands due to their large relative bandwidths. The shorter wavelengths support the realization of arrays with larger element count, enabling pencil beams. Thus, refined spatial sensing, e.g., gesture recognition (touchless interface), 3D mapping (digital twinning), and automotive sensing, become possible in the radio-frequency range, which was susceptible to light and weather conditions in the optical domain [2]. Similar is the case with communication systems. Compared to the conventional microwave bands, high-gain arrays are a natural choice for communication systems operating at mmWave and sub-THz bands to counter the inherently increased path loss at those frequencies. Therefore, the directional steerable beams become favorable for communication links by simultane-

TABLE 3. PAA Performance Metrics and their influence on ISAC Systems

Metric / Feature	Impact on Sensing	Impact on Communication	Relation / Trade-off
Mutual Coupling	↓ Angular estimation and lateral accuracy	↓ Precoding, BER, MIMO decorrelation	Minimizing coupling increases grating lobes and calibration complexity
Grating Lobes	↑ Ambiguities and false targets	→ Usually harmless for FDMA; ↓ SNR	Avoidable by low inter-element spacing; trade-off with mutual coupling
Gain Deviation	↓ Lateral-range accuracy	↓ SNR and spectral efficiency	Joint benefit
Beam Squint	↓ Lateral accuracy	↑ Usability for spatial division multiple access [60]	Critical for radar centric systems
Channel-Reciprocity Fidelity	→ No impact	↑ Channel estimation, inevitable for CRKG [65]	Requires close Tx–Rx PAA spacing; can cause Tx-spillover in monostatic radar
High Array Gain	↑ Detection range	↓ coverage; ↑ SNR and link budget	Best for Radar-assisted comm.; coverage trade-off
Narrow Beamwidth	↑ Angular resolution and DoA estimation	↑ Spatial reuse, ↓ User tracking ability	Radar tracking precision vs. comm. coverage
Beam Steering Range	↑ Wider lateral coverage	↑ Dynamic user-space coverage and scheduling	Larger range reduces gain, increases grating lobes and scanning latency
Low Sidelobe Level	↓ False targets and ghost reflections	↑ Inter-user isolation	Joint benefit; harder to achieve with wide beam scan
Radiation Efficiency	↑ Radar sensing range	↑ SNR	Joint benefit
Element Amplitude & Phase Accuracy	↑ DoA estimation precision	↑ Beamforming and spatial multiplexing efficiency	Joint benefit
Switching / Scan Speed	↑ Fast target tracking	↑ Seamless mobility support and scheduling	Joint benefit; power–speed trade-off may apply
Aperture Size / Element Count	↑ Angular resolution and detection range	↑ SNR and MIMO efficiency	Joint benefit, increased cost and complexity
Calibration Accuracy	↑ Target localization accuracy	↑ Precoding and beam alignment	Joint benefit

Legend - ↑ : Increase, ↓ : Decrease, → : Neutral

ously reinforcing the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and coverage. However, these advantages are available as trade-offs. The higher gain beams have narrow beamwidth, reducing instantaneous coverage in the communication-centric system. EM propagation in mmWave and THz bands suffers severe propagation loss, has poor penetration ability, and is susceptible to blockage, resulting in loss of coverage. In contrast, low-frequency bands offer better range, penetration, and robustness in diverse environments, making them more suitable for wide-area coverage and long-range sensing.

Complex packaging and expensive manufacturing are other drawbacks of mmWave and THz frequencies. Millimeter and sub-millimeter scale wavelengths further reduce the guided material, resulting in making conventional transmission line designs unpractical. For example, at 60 GHz the guided

wavelength in 0.5 mm thick Rogers 4003 substrate (the same substrate used for 10 GHz Butler matrix in Section II-B) becomes shorter than the width of a 50 Ω matched microstrip. Hence the substrate is not suitable for the frequency. Therefore, application-specific redesign of passives and feed networks becomes necessary, as simple frequency scaling of the existing low-frequency designs is often impractical. Additionally, surface mount technology (SMT) lacks suitable lumped components at these frequencies, requiring custom-designed distributed alternatives [68]. The design process is complicated by electrically large components, parasitic effects from interconnects, e.g., bondwires, die bonding, and increased sensitivity to fabrication tolerances. As a result, mmWave and sub-THz bands demand considerably more precision than traditional microwave front-end design.

B. ANTENNA ISOLATORS

A joint challenge in the antenna system design for mono-static radar and in-band full-duplex (IBFD) communication is transmitter spillover. However, conventional communication systems escape this challenge, either using frequency division multiplexing at the cost of the spectrum or using time division duplexing at the cost of data rate. Scalable-aperture sub-array technique has been proposed with digital processing support to enhance isolation between the transmitting and receiving sub-arrays within a single array structure with fixed number of elements [69]. In addition to baseband and digital level self-interference cancellation, the problem can already be mitigated at the antenna system, making it attractive for mono-static radars and IBFD communication. Owing to the weaker received signal, radar systems require adequate Tx-to-Rx isolation since the path loss PL is two times compared to a communication system and further depends upon target cross-section σ as

$$PL = \frac{G_t G_r \lambda^2 \sigma}{(4\pi)^3 R^4} \quad (4)$$

where G_t and G_r are transmitter and receiver antenna gains, respectively, λ is the free-space wavelength and R is the target's single-sided distance.

A straightforward solution is to optimize the placement of the Tx and Rx arrays to maximize isolation. Indented antenna structures have been reported offering Tx-to-Rx isolation up to 30 dB in sub 6 GHz band on the cost of large structures [70]. A brighter opportunity for ISAC is using meta-material technology of electromagnetic bandgap (EBG) structures. Placing these structures between the transmitting and receiving array suppresses the surface wave leakage, electrically isolating the transmitter and receiver antennas on the same substrate. As a proof of concept, authors have reported up to 50 dB of isolation being achieved in K-band using EBG structures between two single radiators compared to 22 dB without EBG [71]. This concept is scalable and can easily be used between the Tx and Rx phased arrays for isolation enhancement. The reported structure is based on a mushroom-type unit cell design where a square metal patch is connected to the bottom ground plane through a via. The mushroom cell acts like a resonator, and its inductance and capacitance can be tuned via size and patch geometry. For the reported design, the realized gain of > 7.5 dB is kept intact while maintaining an isolation of 50 dB between the Tx and Rx radiators separated by 0.75λ . The layout of the structure and results are

FIGURE 7. Designed antenna with EBG structures for an ISAC demo (a) layout, (b) results.

given in Figure 7. For a radar receiver, the received signal strength should preferably be higher than the Tx leakage by a certain amount, depending upon receiver sensitivity and waveform shape. The authors utilized the designed EBG-based antenna system for an ISAC system using FMCW and OFDM waveform. It is noted that with 50 dB of isolation, a performance close to perfect isolation, i.e., no interference at the antenna level, is achievable. The drawback of EBG structures is their narrow bandwidths, limiting their effectiveness in wideband ISAC applications, especially radar-centric designs operating wide bandwidth waveforms for fine resolutions. Introducing EBG units in the PAA can alter the radiation patterns, requiring an EBG unit, element, and array co-design, increasing complexity and limiting design possibilities. Therefore, while EBGs greatly boost isolation in shared antenna setups, their design must be carefully optimized, balancing isolation vs. bandwidth and radiation performance.

C. ANTENNA DUPLEXING

Instead of separate Tx and Rx arrays, a shared TRx array may become essential in certain implementations, e.g., for large-sized arrays, and for specific applications, e.g., channel reciprocity key generation [65], [67]. Passive beamformers and duplexers provide an excellent opportunity for form factor and cost reduction. With a single antenna duplexer applied to the beam-switching matrix, a complete reciprocal structure can be achieved, transmitting and receiving simultaneously. Especially for multi-

band MIMO PAA, the duplexer controls the electrical down-tilt for separate frequency bands, making it possible to steer the beams independently. In contrast, the active beamformers are not reciprocal; therefore, each radiating element requires a duplexer to simultaneously operate the Tx and Rx beamformers.

Antenna duplexing for mono-static radars is achieved through RF switches or circulators. RF switches connecting either receiver or transmitter at a time to the antenna hinder continuous wave (CW) radars and are only helpful for pulsed radars, this type of antenna system can be shared with a time division duplexed communication system. However, continuous wave radars and inband full-duplex (IBFD) communication systems, which are anticipated to be utilized in the future mobile communication generations, share the exact requirement, i.e., a circulator for duplexing purposes. However, typical ferromagnetic circulators are only functional at conventional centimeter wave bands and provide limited bandwidth with bulky size, making them non-compatible with antenna-in-package integration. However, active circulators are implemented in integrated circuits and support millimeter wave band operation; however, they offer limited isolation [72]. An alternative and attractive option is quasi-circulator structures implementable on planar technology, optimized to enhance the isolation between the two ports of the structure and, later on, connected to Tx and Rx ports of the front-end. The idea is to use two isolated ports of a hybrid and to take advantage of the coupled signal with an opposite phase to cancel the leakage signal on the isolated port, as elaborated by the block diagram in Figure 8. This concept is realized through a particular arrangement of hybrid couplers.

The authors evaluate an implementation of a quasi-circulator for the FR3 band with 10 GHz center frequency as given in Figure 8(b). A combination of two hybrid couplers and an un-equal Wilkinson power divider is used on the Isola I-tera substrate, while termination and isolation impedances are obtained using high-frequency thin film resistors from Vishay Intertechnology CH0402 series. In this example design, an isolation up to 30 dB for above 2 GHz bandwidth is measured.

Quasi-circulators are a viable option for limited isolation implantable for conventional frequency bands implementable on PCBs. However, a PCB network of cascaded passive blocks is formidable for mmWave and sub-THz bands, referring to the packaging challenges discussed in Section IV-A. Never-

FIGURE 8. Quasi-circulator (a) block diagram and manufactured prototype, and (b) characterization results.

theless, advanced packaging technologies, e.g., silicon interposers or co-fired ceramics technologies offering thin substrates with fine layout resolutions, are potential options.

The trade-off associated with quasi-circulators is the higher insertion loss, e.g., in the given example, 2.5 dB from antenna-to-receiver in simulation. The measured loss is slightly higher due to a couple of SMA connectors in the path. As the duplexer is the first block after the antenna in a receiver, an insertion loss value in the network equals the added noise figure of the receiver system. This property directly impacts the receiver sensitivity and, hence, the dynamic range. Therefore, it is a critical parameter to be handled in a communication-centric ISAC system. Nevertheless, the transmitter side insertion loss can be compensated with a power amplifier where a subsequent digital level Tx spillover cancellation is present or if the limited Tx leakage is being utilized for Rx synchronization purposes, e.g., as ISAC hardware in [73] uses the minor leakage signal for synchronization.

D. GAIN-BOOSTING LENSES

Apart from beam steering, one advantage of the array is higher gain due to each element's constructive super-position of radiated energy. Recent research has presented an alternate approach for obtaining high gain through a single or limited number of

elements using dielectric lenses [74], [75]. These lenses are generally curved 3D surfaces confining the beam like an optical lens operates for the visible light. Especially for mmWave applications, dielectric lenses have been employed to counteract the higher path loss. In addition to dielectric lenses manufactured by specific materials with fixed curvatures, flat laminate lenses have also been reported exploiting the PCT on commonly available PCBs, designed through metamaterial techniques, hence named as metasurface [75]. These lenses are designed based on subwavelength-sized unit cells manipulating electromagnetic energy's propagation and reflection characteristics. Authors have presented an antenna and its metasurface design for the FR3 band in [76]. Figure 9 shows the layout and results. The unit cell is a circular patch with a sub-wavelength rectangular slot, which controls the polarization and beam pattern filtering, resulting in constructive interference of the radiated energy in the space, enhancing the gain. The metasurface, when held above a patch, becomes a single-layer resonator. The distance is fixed such that the wave bouncing between the ground plane and metasurface combines constructively. This distance is determined by equation 5

$$h+t\sqrt{\epsilon_r} = \frac{(\phi_m + \phi_g)\lambda}{4\pi} + \frac{N\lambda}{2} \quad N = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \quad (5)$$

where h is the distance between the radiator and metasurface, t is the thickness of the metasurface, ϕ_m and ϕ_g are phase magnitudes of reflection from the metasurface and the ground, respectively. The authors achieve a gain boosting from approximately 7 dBi to 16 dBi as plotted in Figure 9(b). Metamaterial lenses are compact and can be printed on the chassis of the wireless device just above the antenna without generally influencing the antenna matching as notable from Figure 9.

The downside of metasurface-based gain-boosting is the restriction on beam-steering opportunities compared to conventional array designs. When excited with a phase difference, multiple antennas under a metasurface produce a tilted beam. However, when striking the metasurface, the tilt wave follows the Snells law, and the reflected portion does not come back on the same angle for constructive interference. An example is shown here with simulation results in Figure 10. For the same metasurface designed by the authors, a beam tilt with a maximum of only $+5^\circ$ and -5° is achieved when exciting both patches with a phase difference of 90° . Another drawback is the interelement coupling originating

FIGURE 9. Designed antenna with metasurface (a) layout configuration, (b) results.

FIGURE 10. Beam steering with metasurface based antenna (a) side view, (b) top view, (c) main beam at -5° and (d) beam at $+5^\circ$.

FIGURE 11. Reflection and transmission coefficient response of antenna with and without the gain boosting lens.

from the lens body. Figure 11 plots the interelement coupling, showing a significant increase in the presence of the lens. This problem hinders its usage in the case of closely placed Tx and Rx antennas (e.g., mono-static radars or in-band full duplex communication) because of high self-interference. Nevertheless, gain-boosting antennas are useful for bi-static sensing and time-duplex communication. For both communication and radars, gain boosting lens can provide added SNR and range; however, the cost of reduced lateral coverage. Such solutions can be beneficial to stationary point-to-point links where a major lateral scan is provided mechanically, e.g., Ship-to-Shore or Ship-to-Ship Naval/Maritime Communication and a fine electronic beam-tilt compensate for ship motion, or between tall towers for fixed-links with wind sway possibility.

E. INTELLIGENT REFLECTIVE SURFACES

Conventional sub-6 GHz communication systems can provide beyond-obstacle communication links with remarkable SNR; however, mmWave bands depend on line-of-sight (LOS) or clean reflected links. The latter case is also valid with beyond-sight target-sensing, e.g., engaging a vehicle around the corner. These services are expected to become possible by beam re-steering using intelligent, reflective surfaces (IRS). These smart surfaces can adapt their behavior to reflect the electromagnetic wave, enabling the wave to reach destinations that are not reachable by the line-of-sight (LOS) links [77]. An IRS-equipped system can replace a large array with a single high-gain radiator using the principle of reflect arrays, i.e., controlling the beam re-steering through the IRS. IRS is in the research phase and is mainly being implemented by meta-materials or adaptation of discrete antenna elements.

Research studies have been done to utilize IRS in the context of ISAC applications [78],[79]. IRS provides the potential for hardware reuse between both systems, joint beamforming, and dynamic environmental adaptation to suit varying demands for either communication or radar. IRS can be a potential groundbreaker in radar-centric ISAC for beyond obstacle target mapping. For communication-centric ISAC, it can also be a key enabler for physical layer security (PhySec) for upcoming mobile communications by introducing an entropy in the channel in a determined way.

The trade-off is the common foreseeable drawbacks of IRS deployment, including increased path loss, greater complexity in RF planning, additional signaling overhead, and the cost associated with

deploying IRS nodes. Beyond these shared limitations, distinct challenges arise in each domain: for communication, channel estimation becomes more complex; for radar, increased latency negatively impacts the accurate mapping of mobile targets. The conflicting requirements lie in the use case scenario, e.g., the need for broad instantaneous coverage for communication versus accurate target mapping for radar. A particular limitation of IRS technology is its limited operational bandwidth. Deploying the IRS in a dynamic environment introduces several operational challenges, particularly due to user mobility. Mobility may lead to ambiguity in determining whether the IRS should operate in the near-field or far-field region, each requiring distinct phase-tuning strategies. This uncertainty and the presence of diffraction effects further complicate the IRS operation in real-time. Additionally, beam squint and beam splitting issues associated with wideband operation need careful attention to ensure effective IRS performance in ISAC applications [80]. Furthermore, a contemporary key challenge is the lack of standardization ensuring seamless IRS operation across different service providers within a shared RF environment.

F. MULTI-DIRECTIONAL BEAMS

A single beam limits the direction of sensing to the direction of communication. Simultaneous multiple beams are achievable using multiple array structures per station. Reference [19] introduces a multi-beam ISAC concept in a radar-centric way. Two distinct PAAs are used for two simultaneous beams; one is dedicated to active sensing, while another is switched between transmitter and receiver for TDD communication.

In this regard, authors propose a multibeam system, depicted in Figure 12 [81]. Using a circulator at each port of the passive beamformer provides an opportunity to independently switch the Tx and Rx beams through their separate multiplexers (Mux) in an IBFD communication. This is an opportunity offered by passive beamformers due to their reciprocity. Such a system can be helpful in relay nodes or base stations serving several users.

G. POLARIZATION DIVERSITY

A promising performance enhancer for ISAC systems is antenna polarization. Rich multipath and fading affect the EM propagation for different polarizations differently. Multiple antenna polarizations, e.g., horizontal and vertical linear polarization or left- and right-hand circular polarization, produce

FIGURE 12. A passive beamformer system with independent transmitter and receiver beams [81].

signals spatially orthogonal to each other, improving propagation robustness and link reliability for communication systems and sensing certainty for radars in dynamic environments.

From a communication standpoint, cross-polarized transmission combats fading and strengthens MIMO performance, theoretically doubling the channel capacity with the same physical antenna aperture [82]. On the sensing front, the polarimetric backscattering can bring additional information about the target, e.g., material classification and surface orientation. Typically, man-made objects exhibit strong co-polarized and patterned cross-polarized EM returns due to their rigid structures and sharp edges compared to natural objects, e.g., water, soil, and vegetation, which exhibit more diffused response [83], [84]. Therefore, sensing using crossed-polarized channels often provides complementary information to the single polarization, especially for the dynamic targets, e.g., bicycles, where rotating wheel spokes and metal frame originate a degree of cross-polarized EM returns. This property is helpful in vehicular ISAC scenarios for determining the object's nature, e.g., a pedestrian vs a bicycle, and furthermore, decisions for communication pairing with the target, e.g., in the case of a car in the range.

Polarimetric MIMO automotive radar has been designed and comprehensively studied in [85] for the 77 GHz band. Their study reveals that various road users leave distinct polarimetric scattering signatures on the backscattered signals, which is helpful for target identification. For instance, cyclists and motorcyclists were found to have cross-polarization channel correlation ≈ 0.95 , higher than for pedestrians ≈ 0.88 .

In conclusion, exploiting the polarization diversity boosts the communication systems' channel capacity while enabling target classification for the radars, hence a joint performance enhancement fea-

ture for ISAC. However, the trade-off is significantly complex in PAA design and signal processing. PAA challenges include maintaining polarization isolation, individual phase and amplitude calibration for each polarization, and polarization selection and switching to adapt to the real-time operational conditions, e.g., communication throughput or sensing accuracy. In the context of ISAC, authors have reported a polarization agile antenna solution for 28 GHz with switchable horizontal, vertical, and circular polarizations [86].

Table 4 summarizes the key enablers for ISAC antenna sharing based on use cases and the associated challenges. Similarly to other hardware, the PAA systems are also prone to imperfections, some of which are discussed in Section III. In addition, there are manufacturing imperfections. Dedicated digital processing and a phase array system are desirable to mitigate hardware imperfections, e.g., antenna calibration, element failure indication, etc.

V. FUTURE WORK

The sharing of resources is of prime importance for ISAC in meeting the expanding demands of wireless technologies. Building on the work presented in this paper, multiple promising research avenues remain open for future exploration. This section presents a summary of a few relevant research directions for PAAs to support the upcoming generation of ISAC systems:

- **THz frequencies** can enable terabit per second data rates and sub-millimeter radar imaging resolutions. THz PAA must address challenges such as photonic circuits for beamforming, high-speed switching through graphene and liquid crystals, and sub-millimeter scale packaging with sufficient gain.
- **AI-assistance** can be a paradigm shift for PAAs. Since ISAC systems require agile adaptability in dynamic environments, AI predictive mutual-coupling mitigation, beam management, calibration, beam-squint, or null-avoidance can enhance system responsiveness and fidelity in real time.
- **On-chip quasi-circulators and duplexers** can enable monostatic sensing and in-band full duplex communication in compact packaging. CMOS integration of magnet-free circulators through spatiotemporal modulation and electrically balanced duplexers presents an encouraging line of future research.
- **Intelligent Reflecting Surfaces (IRS)** can revolution RF planning and base station deploy-

TABLE 4. Key Enablers for ISAC Antenna Sharing

Technology	Impact on Sensing	Impact on Communication	Trade-offs / Challenges
mmWave Front-ends	↑ Range resolution	↑ Datarate spatial multiplexing, ↓ Instantaneous coverage	Path loss, packaging complexity, blockage
EBG isolators	↑ Reception quality	↑ full-duplex performance	Limited bandwidth, radiation-pattern distortion
Antenna Duplexers	↑ Single aperture monostatic, ↓ Reception quality	↑ Shared Tx/Rx antenna, integration with passive BF	Limited isolation, insertion loss
Metamaterial Lenses	↑ Range, ↓ Lateral scan	↑ Link budget, ↓ Instantaneous coverage	Formfactor, complexity for wideband coverage
IRS	↑ Sensing diversity, ↑ NLOS target mapping	↑ Channel conditions, coverage	Infrastructure, latency, coordination
Multi-directional Beams	↑ Multiple targets tracking	↑ Multi-user MIMO	Lower per beam gain
Polarization Diversity	↑ Detection in multipath, clutter rejection	↑ Robustness	Complex antenna design, complex signal processing

Legend - ↑ : Increase, ↓ : Decrease, → : Neutral

ment. IRS can enable reduced PAA complexity with enriched MIMO for channel capacity and extended beamforming beyond target obstacle detection. IRS is in the early research phase; only a few prototypes are commercially available. Future research should investigate joint RIS-PAA design and standardization.

- **Orbital Angular Momentum (OAM) diversity** is a novel approach beyond polarization diversity. OAM beams are EM waves with twisted wavefronts and can isolate radar and communication signals on the same carrier. OAM modes can be excited through circular antenna arrays, helical antennas, or dielectric lenses. The concept is in the initial stages and needs research attention for validation in various environments and use cases.

VI. CONCLUSION

PAA systems are widely used for communication and radar systems; however, they have their respective antenna requirements. Typical radars prefer a narrow beam with swift sweeps for lateral resolution, while communication systems use stable beams with specific beam widths to ensure coverage. Still, PAA sharing in an ISAC system has prospects that reduce the cost and form factor. This work briefs the reader on the hardware challenges and possibilities of utilizing a shared PAA for both systems in an ISAC scenario. A brief overview of the state-of-the-art is presented, comprising the reported array

of design techniques in planar technology, mainly PCT, with wide beam scans and practical integration into the device size of today. Active and passive BFN network approaches are summarized. However, active BFNs outshine the passives in performance with energy consumption and hardware cost. Passive beamformers, mainly due to their limited beam pointings, are understated in the literature. Nonetheless, they are an option for battery-operated devices to have limited beam-pointings compared to the presently used nearly omnidirectional energy radiation. Moreover, a single BFN can serve as Tx and Rx due to reciprocity, a property that active BFN lacks. In this regard, the authors develop and evaluate a conventional Butler matrix. Realizing an array out of the stand-alone single elements has associated hitches. This article indicates the technical complications of a conventional PAA system, such as mutual coupling, grating lobes, gain fluctuation, and beam squint, and their impact on sensing and communication performances. Contemporary mitigation solutions for the design challenges are summarized, and PAA performance matrices are developed for ISAC. From the discussion, it is deduced that the application-specific element design is of utmost importance; if properly designed, it automatically reduces the challenge at the array level. The emerging technologies provide a bunch of key enablers for PAA sharing in ISAC. Millimeter wave and sub-THz technology is on top, which already utilizes pointing beams in communication links to counteract the path

loss, a beam property desirable in radars. Antenna isolators and duplexers help mitigate the transmitter spillover and enable PAA sharing among monostatic radars and IBFD communication. In this regard, the authors present an EBG isolator and a quasi-circulator. Metamaterial lenses can be helpful where the array is mainly used for gain-boosting; however, it complicates the beamforming, elaborated in this work through a simulation study. Further key enablers include IRS for beyond obstacle link and sensing, multi-beams through passive BF, and polarization diversity with polarimetric sensing. In conclusion, with state-of-the-art antenna solutions, PAA sharing among communication and sensing can be balanced with some trade-offs. Exploiting cutting-edge technologies, there is no major roadblock to antenna sharing in ISAC; however, case-specific research and development are required to enable it in consumer applications. Moreover, emerging technologies are making PAA sharing practical and desirable.

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